

Postpartum Stress Causes and Solutions

Juraeva Dildora Nasirdinovna

Scientific adviser, Departments of Pedagogy and Psychology, Tashkent Medical Academy, Uzbekistan, Tashkent

Quvondiqova Sadoqat Vakhobjonovna

2nd year student, Faculty of Pediatrics, Tashkent Medical Academy, Uzbekistan, Tashkent

Annotation: A number of emotional changes are observed in women after childbirth. For example, there may be situations such as crying for no reason, irritability, sleep disturbance, increased panic. Sometimes this condition can go away without the help of a medical psychologist and is manifested by fatigue. In this case, a woman needs the love and attention of her husband and family members.

Keywords: postpartum stress, depression, childbirth, medical psychologist, hormonal changes, emotion.

INTRODUCTION

Childbirth is one of the greatest life experiences for a woman. But for some women, this experience can cause stress, anxiety and mental pressure. Postpartum stress is also commonly referred to as "postnatal stress" or "postpartum stress" and is related to the mental, emotional and physical changes that occur in a woman after childbirth.

There are several causes of postpartum stress. They can be:

1. **Hormonal changes:** After childbirth, the level of hormones in a woman's body changes dramatically. Declines in estrogen and progesterone can affect mood and increase mood swings and stress.
2. **Physiological fatigue:** Childbirth is a great physical burden for a woman's body. Fatigue, lack of sleep and lack of energy take time for the body to recover. The round-the-clock work of caring for a newborn can add to the stress.
3. **Responsibilities of motherhood:** Responsibilities such as taking care of a newborn baby, breastfeeding, proper care can be overwhelming for some mothers. The fear of responsibility, the feeling of not being a good enough mother, causes stress.
4. **Lack of social support:** Inadequate support from loved ones, feelings of loneliness and isolation increase stress. Especially women who lack the support of parents or loved ones may experience more stress.
5. **Negative childbirth experience:** Complicated childbirth, drastic interventions (for example, cesarean or vacuum delivery) or problems related to the baby's health can evoke traumatic feelings in a woman. After these processes, stress increases.

It is important not to ignore the signs of postpartum stress. Some of the main symptoms may include:

Excessive worry: A woman's persistent worry about future events, the health of her baby, or her duties as a mother.

Insomnia: Insomnia is not only related to baby care, but also due to incessant anxiety and inner restlessness in a woman.

Mood changes: Unexpected feelings of joy and sadness, frequent crying or depression.

Severe fatigue: Despite the recovery of physical strength after childbirth, mental fatigue can be severe. Such a situation can be one of the main causes of stress.

Self-blame: A woman may blame herself for not being a good enough mother or for not being able to provide enough care for the child.

Avoiding asking for help: Sometimes women may be reluctant to ask for help or share their feelings with loved ones in an attempt to hide their stress.

Ways to overcome postpartum stress:

1. **Emotional support:** in times of stress, a woman may not be able to tell her inner feelings and fears to her loved ones. In such cases, it is necessary for a woman's relatives to talk more and listen to her, especially her husband.
2. **Medical help:** If postpartum stress is developing into severe depression or mental health problems, it's important to seek professional help. Psychotherapy, such as cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), or medication can help manage stress and depression.
3. **Improve rest and sleep patterns:** After childbirth, a woman's body needs rest and recovery. Resting as much as possible while taking care of the baby, filling the free time with scheduled sleep will reduce stress.
4. **Postpartum Exercise:** Light exercise such as walking, yoga, and breathing techniques have positive effects on mental and physical health. Exercise improves mood and reduces stress hormones.
5. **Nutrition:** Eating a healthy diet and drinking enough fluids are important in managing stress and mood. Women should pay attention to foods rich in vitamins and minerals in order to eat a balanced diet and feel good about themselves. In addition, I would say to women: Relax the demands on yourself: Everything must be perfect give up the idea that. This process is learned in time, every mother finds her own way. Take time out from time to time: Sometimes taking time for yourself and focusing on yourself will reduce stress and increases mental alertness. Appreciate Small Accomplishments: Celebrating your small accomplishments every day and appreciating your successes will help you beat stress.

CONCLUSION:

Although postpartum stress is a natural process, it is important to ensure that it is recognized and managed in time. Emotional and physical support, a healthy lifestyle and psychological support can help a woman go through the postpartum period more easily. Prolonged stress can lead to depression or mental health problems, so in such cases it is necessary to consult a specialist.

REFERENCES:

1. Z.Ibodullayev "Tibbiyot psixalogiyasi"
2. Y.M.Fayziyev "Umumiy va tibbiy psixalogiya"
3. Andrew M. Pomerantz "Clinical Psychology"
4. Helen Dent "Clinical Psychology"
5. Psychological problems of patients with cancer – PubMed
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20562751/>
6. "Tibbiy psixologiya" - A. Sattorov
7. "Psixologiya asoslari" - O. Tursunov
8. "Psixologiya va hayot" - M. Mahkamov
9. "Salomatlik psixologiyasi" - A. Yo'ldoshev
10. "Shaxs psixologiyasi" - X. Jo'raev

11. "Handbook of Clinical Health Psychology" - Susan Ayers
12. "Health Psychology" - Shelley Taylor
13. "The Psychology of Health and Illness" - Keith J. Petrie & John A. Weinman
14. "Medical Psychology: Psychological Factors in Physical Disease" - Alan Stoudemire
15. "The Oxford Handbook of Health Psychology" - Howard S. Friedman